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SEARCH REPORT

Request No: TR 2014/112	Date of Receipt: 05 June 2015 (05.06.2015)
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Application No 2013/04993	Filing date (day/month/year) 26 April 2013 (26.04.2013)	(Earliest) Priority Date (day/month/year)
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Applicant(s)
ERDAL CAN ALKOCLAR et al.

Title of invention
A composition for treatment of viral infection

This search report consists of a total of 2 sheets

It is also accompanied by a copy of each prior art document cited in this report 18 sheets

1. Search on the State of the Art
 Additional search on the State of the Art
2. All claims were found searchable
 Certain claims were found unsearchable, see Box I
3. Certain explanations to the search report, see Box II
4. The application concerns:
 - pharmaceutical products/substances or their process of preparation
 - veterinary products/substances or their process of preparation

SEARCH REPORT

Application No
2013/04993

A. CLASSIFICATION OF SUBJECT MATTER *A61K 31/7034 (2015.01)*
~~*A61K 31/015 (2006.01)*~~
A61P 31/12 (2006.01)

According to International Patent Classification (IPC)

B. FIELDS SEARCHED

Minimum documentation searched (classification system followed by classification symbols)
A61K 31/7034, A61K 31/015, A61P 31/12

Electronic data base consulted during the search (name of data base and, where practicable, search terms used)
PatSearch (RUPTO internal), USPTO, PAJ, Espacenet, Information Retrieval System of FIPS

C. DOCUMENTS CONSIDERED TO BE RELEVANT

Category*	Citation of document, with indication, where appropriate, of the relevant passages	Relevant to claim No
Y A	CN 101322715 A (KUNMING INSTITUTE OF BOTANY et al.) 17.12.2008, abstract	1, 3, 4, 6 2, 5
Y A	YOO YC et al. Protective effect of ginsenoside-Rb2 from Korean red ginseng on the lethal infection of haemagglutinating virus of Japan in mice. J Ginseng Res. 2013 Mar; 37(1):80-6, abstract, fig. 1, 4, p. 82, last par., p. 84, left col.	1, 3, 4, 6 2, 5
A	DAE-GOON Yoo et al. Protective Effect of Korean Red Ginseng Extract on the Infections by H1N1 and H3N2 Influenza Viruses in Mice. J Med Food 15 (10) 2012, 855-862	1-6

Further documents are listed in the continuation of Box C.

See patent family annex

* Special categories of cited documents:

"A" document defining the general state of the art which is not considered to be of particular relevance
"P" document published prior to the filing date but later than the priority date claimed
"X" document of particular relevance; the claimed invention cannot be considered novel or cannot be considered to involve an inventive step when the document is taken alone

" Y " document of particular relevance; the claimed invention cannot be considered to involve an inventive step when the document is combined with one or more other such documents, such combination being obvious to a person skilled in the art
"&" document member of the same patent family

Date of mailing of the search report: 05 October 2015 (05.10.2015)

Name and mailing address of the
International Searching Authority
FIPS
30-1, Berezhkovskaya nab., G-59, GSP-3, Moscow, 125993, RU
Facsimile No. (499) 243-33-37

Authorized officer

D. Igumnov

Telephone No. (499) 240-25-91